

What can we learn from the Public Health England COVID-19 reports?

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Abstract

During the latter part of 2021, Public Health England published weekly reports that included some actual data on infection rates. These show that about three months after receiving a second dose of one of the vaccines available in the UK, unless a timely third booster vaccine is administered, infection risk is greater than if one had remained completely unvaccinated. The apparent negative efficacy can be explained by antibody-dependent enhancement.

Case Rates

Public Health England (PHE) and latterly the UK Health Security Agency which took over the role publish weekly reports of the progress of the COVID-19 pandemic and the effect of the vaccination programme [1]. Vaccine effectiveness is estimated by comparing rates of disease in vaccinated individuals to rates in unvaccinated. Continuous monitoring is important because the effectiveness of vaccines in the “real world” may differ from that found in the clinical trials which had relatively short follow-up [1]. Helpfully, during the latter part of 2021 (weeks 36 to 51, inclusive), the reports included explicit rates of infection within each of seven adult age groups. In particular, the data include the infection rates per 10⁵ persons who were “fully” vaccinated¹ and amongst those who were unvaccinated. From these we calculate the logarithmic relative risk (LRR) of reported infection amongst fully vaccinated persons with respect to unvaccinated.

$$\text{LRR}[\text{vaccinated}:\text{unvaccinated}] = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{rate}[\text{vaccinated}]}{\text{rate}[\text{unvaccinated}]} \right) \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 plots the LRR for each adult age group against time. We see a steadily increasing relative risk of detected infection across all age groups during the first half of the study period. The risk is lower for the youngest because they received their second dose later than the older groups: see Figure 2 which is derived from the cumulative uptake graphs for 2021 provided in the reports. During the second half of the study period the risk decreases for those aged over 50 years, the gradient of descent being steeper with age. This corresponds to the roll-out of the third “booster” dose of vaccine. For those over the age of 80 years it started on about week 38 and reached 50% uptake by about week 41. Younger age groups received their third dose up to ten weeks later and with a lower final uptake.

¹Two doses fourteen or more days before testing.

Figure 1: *Logarithmic relative risk (LRR) of reported infection for the latter part of 2021.*

Figure 2: *Weekly dose-2 uptake by age group.*

Surprisingly, according to the published data, the LRR was actually positive for all age groups at some point during the study period. In other words, vaccination was apparently associated with an increased rate of detected infection. The exact time-course of the response to full vaccination is, however, obscured by the staggered roll-out of the second dose, both between age groups and within age groups. Reconstruction of the LRR trajectory entails deconvolution.

LRR Response

Let the LRR response to full vaccination be a function $f(x, y)$ of the weeks (x) since the second dose and the age group (y). Thus $x=0$ means that infection is detected in the very same week that dose 2 is administered. Parameter y ranges from 0 to 6 according to the age group:

y	Ages
0	18–29
1	30–39
2	40–49
3	50–59
4	60–69
5	70–79
6	80+

The convoluted LRR on week w ($36 \leq w \leq 51$) is given by $F(w, y)$ where

$$F(w, y) = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sum_{k=1}^w g(k, y) 10^{f(w-k, y)}}{\sum_{k=1}^w g(k, y)} \right) \quad (2)$$

and where, for any w and y , $g(w, y)$ is the uptake of dose 2 on week w amongst age group y . The denominator is thus simply the cumulative uptake on the particular week as read from the published graphs; the roll-out of the second dose did not begin until week 1 of 2021. Notice that it is necessary to take the antilogarithm of $f(w-k, y)$ first before calculating the weighted sum. This is because when groups are merged relative risks are linearly additive whereas their logarithms are not. The predicted LRR estimate is then obtained by taking the logarithm of the convolution. We choose function f to minimize the total square error E between the predicted and the observed LRRs over the 16 weeks in the study period and over all age groups.

$$E = \sum_{w=36}^{51} \sum_{y=0}^6 (F(w, y) - \text{LRR}(w, y))^2 \quad (3)$$

where $\text{LRR}(w, y)$ is the observed LRR (Figure 1).

The dose 2 uptake distributions (Figure 2) are temporally staggered. Thus the observed LRRs in each age group reveal a different part of the underlying LRR response: the youngest and oldest age groups provide information mostly about the early and late responses, respectively. Therefore we assume a shared model in which the LRR response is a cubic function of time but with an initial value that is specific to the particular age group. Without the latter, the fit is poor. The residual efficacy from the first dose thus appears to be different in each age group, perhaps reflecting different viral exposures. Thus we have ten parameters altogether, $c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4, c_5, c_6, k_1, k_2, k_3$, where

$$f(x, y) = c_y + k_1 x + k_2 x^2 + k_3 x^3 \quad (4)$$

Using the Nelder-Mead optimization algorithm² starting with the zero vector of parameters, the minimum error achieved was $E=0.3968$ with the function shown in Figure 3.

²As implemented by the `minimize` function of Python's SciPy module.

Figure 3: *Predicted logarithmic relative risk (LRR) of reported infection after dose 2 compared to unvaccinated.*

Figure 4: *Comparison of observed LRR and predicted, $F(w, y)$.*

Figure 1 shows for comparison the convoluted response function $F(w, y)$ overlaid on the trajectories of the observed LRRs shown in Figure 4. The correspondence is fairly close. Therefore the function shown in Figure 3 is a reasonable indication of the actual response to the second dose. By the time the second dose is administered, the residual protection from the first dose corresponds to an efficacy of around 20%. The second dose quickly improves the protection, achieving an efficacy of 70% or more in the older age groups. This is broadly consistent with the earlier observational studies [2, 3, 4, 5] that PHE references in its various reports. These report efficacies of 60%–72% of the vaccines at preventing infection, but all the studies have a short follow-up period of less than 59 days from vaccination. This means that they correspond to only the initial part of the trajectory shown in Figure 3. Furthermore, those early studies were of the Alpha variant whereas the PHE data refer to the Delta against which the vaccines are less effective [6].

However, after about seven weeks the protection wanes and after about 15 weeks is zero. Worse still, the LRR continues to rise such that after about 27 weeks from the second dose the efficacy is around -100%. The situation does not improve until the third dose is administered and then the LRR falls rapidly below zero.

Negative Efficacy

The observation that vaccine efficacy at preventing infection becomes negative is unexpected and requires explanation. It has been suggested that this is an artefact of the way that PHE estimate the number of unvaccinated persons [7]. PHE do this for each age group by subtracting the number who have been vaccinated with a first dose from the total in the national database, the National Immunisation Management System (NIMS). However, it is suggested that the NIMS database is inflated with spurious records and duplications and as a consequence the apparent infection rate among unvaccinated persons is grossly underestimated. Nevertheless, PHE has gone to considerable lengths to purge NIMS of duplicates and invalid records. Indeed a validation study concluded that NIMS is highly accurate and complete [8]. Consequently NIMS appears to be regarded as a more accurate and up-to-date source of relevant vaccine demographics than even the Office for National Statistics [9].

However, we can check whether the observed positive LRR values are plausible without relying on estimates of population size: we use partially vaccinated cases as the control rather than unvaccinated. This is possible because during the 16-week study period, PHE also published the number of new cases in each age group who had received their first vaccine dose within the previous three weeks. Regrettably PHE did not state the total numbers of persons who had recently received the first dose, so calculation of the actual infection rates is problematic. Nevertheless PHE did publish the cumulative uptakes of dose 1 each week in graphical form from which the values can be read using pixel coordinates. These provide sufficient information for at least approximate estimates. As we will see, the results are similar to those using unvaccinated persons as the control.

Dose 1 Uptake

In order to determine the number of persons in any given age group who have received their first dose in the preceding three weeks, we must subtract the cumulative uptake from that three weeks prior. However, the differences are small, especially for the older age groups which had virtually finished receiving first doses by the beginning of the study period. As we are limited to reading the cumulative uptakes from the pixel coordinates of the graphs in the absence of explicit numbers, we must smooth the raw data before subtracting. We therefore fit a regular polynomial function to the cumulative uptakes by least-squares optimization. Graphs of the residuals for each age group (Figures 10–16) are shown in an appendix on page 15. The preferred degree of polynomial is shown in green; the residuals associated with a degree one less and one more are shown for comparison in blue and red, respectively.

Preferred Degree	
Age group	Degree
18-29	3
30-39	4
40-49	3
50-59	3
60-69	2
70-79	2
80+	1

For any given week w and age group y , let $G(w, y)$ be the cumulative uptake of dose 1 as specified by the corresponding polynomial function. The estimated number of persons who have received their first dose within the previous three weeks is thus given by

$$\text{number}[\text{recent-dose-1}] = (G(w, y) - G(w-3, y)) \times N(y) \quad (5)$$

where $N(y)$ is the total size of age group y in NIMS [10].

Recent Dose 1

PHE determine the vaccination status of each reported case by linking it to a record in NIMS on the basis of the NHS number. This was not always possible and so PHE make the reasonable assumption of statistical independence between linkage and infection risk. This means that the number of detected cases with a particular vaccination status can be corrected proportionately. The rate is multiplied by the ratio of total cases to linked cases. Following this same procedure, the estimated infection rate per 10^5 persons who have received dose 1 within the previous three weeks is thus given by

$$\text{rate}[\text{recent-dose-1}] = \frac{\text{cases}[\text{recent-dose-1}]}{\text{number}[\text{recent-dose-1}]} \times \frac{\text{cases}[\text{total}]}{\text{cases}[\text{total}] - \text{cases}[\text{unlinked}]} \times 10^5 \quad (6)$$

The corresponding LRR using this new reference group is thus

$$\text{LRR}[\text{vaccinated}:\text{recent-dose-1}] = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{rate}[\text{vaccinated}]}{\text{rate}[\text{recent-dose-1}]} \right) \quad (7)$$

Figure 5 plots the modified LRR. Although there is considerably more noise as one would expect given the smaller control group sizes and error inherent in reading uptakes from a graph, the results are broadly similar to those when using unvaccinated persons as the control (Figure 1). The LRR is positive at some point during the study period in all age groups. Inflation of population size cannot account for this as the infection rate in the control group is no longer calculated by subtraction. The most plausible explanation for the LRR rising prior to the administration of the third dose appears to be waning antibody levels. Furthermore, antibody-dependent enhancement (ADE) at sub-neutralizing whole-spike antibody levels would explain why the LRR values become positive; indeed, concern about the possibility of ADE was expressed during early development of the vaccines [11, 12].

Figure 5: *Logarithmic relative risk (LRR) of reported infection for the latter part of 2021.*

When fitting Equation 4 to the modified LRR the minimum error ($E=1.2000$) was greater than before as one would expect given the increased amount of noise in the observations, but the resulting response function (Figure 6) was similar to the previous one; the predictions and observations are plotted for comparison in Figure 7.

The most notable difference between Figures 3 and 6 is that the initial values are slightly more positive in the latter. Therefore let us compare recent dose 1 risk to that of no vaccination at all. Figure 8 shows that at the start of the study period recent first dose is associated with a positive LRR in all age groups. This then decays over the course of the following 16 weeks. What could explain this?

Figure 6: *Predicted logarithmic relative risk (LRR) of reported infection after dose 2 compared to recent dose 1.*

Figure 7: *Comparison of observed LRR and predicted, $F(w, y)$.*

Figure 8: *Logarithmic relative risk (LRR) after recent dose-1.*

Explanation

The positive LRR seen in all age groups after recent first dose might be attributable to increased risk-taking behaviour resulting from the false reassurance of being vaccinated. However, if we disregard the older age groups whose trajectories are subject to a large amount of noise, we see a consistent downward trend during the study period; there is no obvious reason why there should be a marked diminution of any risk-taking effect during the study period. Equally, if the positive LRR were due to overestimation of population size we would expect it to rise further with time, not fall, as the proportion of vaccinated persons increases and the error associated with subtraction amplifies. This leaves ADE as the only remaining explanation for increased risk immediately after receiving the first dose before antibody levels have reached a neutralizing level. Why though should the LRR decrease?

One possible reason is that persons who have been previously infected respond differently to the first dose than those who have not. It seems plausible that ADE is seen after the first dose only in those who have never been infected, but is this hypothesis consistent with the data? Many unvaccinated persons had been infected by the start of the study period and we can estimate the proportion of each age group who became infected during the course of the subsequent 16 weeks. If we assume that previous infection is highly protective against reinfection for at least a few months, with reference to any particular age group we can determine the proportion p_w on week w that have been infected since the start of the study period by summation of the infection rates each week.

$$p_w = 10^{-5} \sum_{w'=36}^w \text{rate}[\text{unvaccinated}]_{w'} \quad (8)$$

Figure 9 plots this for each age group and shows that a significant proportion did get infected during the study period, especially amongst younger persons. The average proportion of adults under the age of 50 years who got infected was approximately 0.15.

Figure 9: *Cumulative proportion of unvaccinated persons who have tested positive since week 36.*

A Formal Model

The number of unvaccinated persons becoming infected during the study period is indeed significant. In order to explore further the hypothesis that this accounts for the positive but falling LDDs we require a mathematical model that can be tested against the observed data.

For a given age group on any particular week w the relative risk (which we will abbreviate to RR_w) of infection amongst those who have recently received dose 1 compared to the unvaccinated is given by

$$RR_w = \frac{(1-p_w)r'_w + p_w s'_w}{(1-p_w)r_w + p_w s_w} \quad (9)$$

where

r'_w = “infection rate among recent dose-1 recipients who have not been infected”

s'_w = “infection rate among recent dose-1 recipients who have been infected”

r_w = “infection rate among unvaccinated persons who have not been infected”

s_w = “infection rate among unvaccinated persons who have been infected”

We now make some modelling assumptions.

Assumption 1

Among persons who have not been infected, the relative risk of infection associated with recent dose 1 compared to being unvaccinated is a constant α .

$$\forall w \bullet \frac{r'_w}{r_w} = \alpha \quad (10)$$

Assumption 2

Among persons who have been infected, the relative risk of infection associated with recent dose 1 compared to being unvaccinated is a constant β .

$$\forall w \bullet \frac{s'_w}{s_w} = \beta \quad (11)$$

Assumption 3

Among persons who are unvaccinated, the relative risk of primary infection compared to reinfection is a constant γ .

$$\forall w \bullet \frac{r_w}{s_w} = \gamma \quad (12)$$

Now, substituting from Equations 10 and 11 into Equation 9 and writing \bar{p}_w as a shorthand for $(1-p_w)$,

$$\text{RR}_w = \frac{\bar{p}_w \alpha r_w + p_w \beta s_w}{\bar{p}_w r_w + p_w s_w} \quad (13)$$

and rearranging,

$$\frac{p_w(\beta - \text{RR}_w)}{\bar{p}_w(\text{RR}_w - \alpha)} = \frac{r_w}{s_w} \quad (14)$$

But the above is equal to γ (Equation 12). So, applying Assumption 3 to particular cases of w ,

$$\frac{p_{36}(\beta - \text{RR}_{36})}{\bar{p}_{36}(\text{RR}_{36} - \alpha)} = \frac{p_{51}(\beta - \text{RR}_{51})}{\bar{p}_{51}(\text{RR}_{51} - \alpha)} \quad (15)$$

With reference to Figure 8 we see that for adults aged less than 50 years, RR_{36} is about 1.75 (LRR=0.2430) and RR_{51} is about 1.15 (LRR=0.0607). In order to demonstrate that the model is a viable explanation for the trajectories of LRR observed in Figure 8 we need only to provide plausible values for the remaining variables that satisfy Equation 15. We suggest $p_{36}=0.80$ since it is generally thought that the majority of persons have been infected at some point during the pandemic. This implies that $p_{51}=0.95$ since a further 15% of the unvaccinated appear to have become infected during the study period. Furthermore, we assume that the first dose rapidly confers additional protection to persons who have been previously infected: $\beta=0.20$. Substituting these values into Equation 15 and solving for α we obtain

$$\alpha = 2.06 \quad (16)$$

In other words, on average during the first three weeks after administration of the first dose to a person who has never been infected, the risk of infection is paradoxically more than doubled. Substituting the values into the LHS of Equation 15 we obtain

$$\gamma = 19.75 \tag{17}$$

This is consistent with the assumption, on which Figure 9 rests, that previous infection is highly protective against reinfection at least for the duration of the study period.

Discussion

We have focussed here entirely on reported infections. The results show that vaccination with two doses is associated within a matter of months with negative efficacy at preventing detected infection. These results are comparable to the findings of another study of the UK data [13]. They are inconsistent with overinflation of population size estimates that has been proposed as an explanation for the observed negative efficacy [7]. The most plausible explanation appears to be that ADE occurs when antibody levels fall below a neutralizing level. This also explains the negative efficacy seen in the first few weeks after the administration of first dose to a person who has never been previously infected. This underlines the importance of achieving and maintaining a neutralizing level of antibody. Despite the efficacy of vaccines at preventing serious illness as shown in trials, high rates of infection make contact tracing impractical, are a particular danger to persons who are immunosuppressed and/or unable to be vaccinated, exacerbate the potential risk of long covid, and increase the likelihood of dangerous new variants of SARS-CoV-2 arising which might possibly evade current vaccines.

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References

- [1] **Public Health England.** COVID-19 vaccine weekly surveillance reports. *GOV.UK* (2022) <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/covid-19-vaccine-weekly-surveillance-reports>
- [2] **Pritchard E, Matthews PC, Stoesser N, Eyre DW, Gethings O, Vihta KD, Jones J, House T, VanSteenHouse H, Bell I, Bell JI, Newton JN, Farrar J, Diamond I, Rourke E, Studley R, Crook D, Peto T, Walker SA, Pouwels KB.** Impact of vaccination on new SARS-CoV-2 infections in the UK. *medRxiv preprint* (2021) June 9. <https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.04.22.21255913v2>
- [3] **Hall VJ, Foulkes S, Saei A, Andrews N, Oguti B, Charlett A, Wellington E, Stowe J, Gillson N, Atti A, Islam J, Karagiannis I, Munro K, Khawam J, Chand MA, Brown CS, Ramsay M, Lopez-Bernal J, Hopkins S, SIREN Study Group.** COVID-19 vaccine coverage in health-care workers in England and effectiveness of BNT162b2 mRNA

- vaccine against infection (SIREN): a prospective, multicentre, cohort study. *Lancet* (2021) **397** 1725–35.
[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736\(21\)00790-X/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS0140-6736(21)00790-X/fulltext)
- [4] **Shrotri M, Krutikov M, Palmer T, Giddings R, Azmi B, Subbarao S, Fuller C, Irwin-Singer A, Davies D, Tut G, Bernal JL, Moss P, Hayward A, Copas A, Shallcross L.** Vaccine effectiveness of the first dose of ChAdOx1 nCoV-19 and BNT162b2 against SARS-CoV-2 infection in residents of long-term care facilities in England (VIVALDI): a prospective cohort study. *Lancet Infectious Diseases* (2021) **21** 1529–38.
[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099\(21\)00289-9/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099(21)00289-9/fulltext)
- [5] **Menni C, Klaser K, May A, Polidori L, Capdevila J, Louca P, Sudre CH, Nguyen LH, Drew DA, Merino J, Hu C, Selvachandran S, Antonelli M, Murray B, Canas LS, Molteni E, Graham MS, Modat M, Joshi AD, Mangino M, Hammers A, Goodman AL, Chan AT, Wolf J, Steves CJ, Valdes AM, Ourselin S, Spector TD.** Vaccine side-effects and SARS-CoV-2 infection after vaccination in users of the COVID Symptom Study app in the UK: a prospective observational study. *Lancet Infectious Diseases* (2021) **21** 939–49.
[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099\(21\)00224-3/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/laninf/article/PIIS1473-3099(21)00224-3/fulltext)
- [6] **Hayawi K, Shahriar S, Serhani MA, Alashwal H, Masud MM.** Vaccine versus Variants (3Vs): Are the COVID-19 Vaccines Effective against the Variants? A Systematic Review. *Vaccines* (2021) **9** 1305–22.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34835238/>
- [7] **Spiegelhalter D, Masters A.** Take care with claims about unvaccinated case rates. *The Guardian Newspaper* (2021).
<https://www.theguardian.com/theobserver/commentisfree/2021/sep/19/take-care-with-claims-about-unvaccinated-case-rates-covid>
- [8] **Tessier E, Stowe J, Tsang C, Rai Y, Clarke E, Lakhani A, Makwana A, Heard H, Rickard T, Kirsebom F, Quinot C, Lakhani S, Power L, Edelstein M, Evans A, Ramsay M, Lopez-Bernal J, White J, Gower C, Andrews N, Campbell C.** Monitoring the COVID-19 immunisation programme through a National Immunisation Management System — England’s experience. *medRxiv preprint* (2021) 22nd September.
<https://www.medrxiv.org/content/medrxiv/early/2021/09/22/2021.09.14.21263578.full.pdf>
- [9] **Tessier E, Rai Y, Clarke E, Lakhani A, Tsang C, Makwana A, Heard H, Rickard T, Lakhani S, Partho R, Edelstein M, Ramsay M, Lopez-Bernal J, White J, Andrews N, Campbell CNJ, Stowe J.** Characteristics associated with COVID-19 vaccine uptake among adults aged 50 years and above in England (8 December 2020—17 May 2021): a population-level observational study. *BMJ Open* (2022) **22**:e055278.
<https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/bmjopen/12/3/e055278.full.pdf>
- [10] **UK Health Security Agency.** Weekly national Influenza and COVID-19 surveillance report Week 50 report (up to week 49 data): 16 December 2021. *GOV.UK* (2021) Table 10 Page 82.

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1041447/Weekly_Flu_and_COVID-19_report_w50.pdf#page=82

- [11] **Hotez PJ, Corry DB, Bottazi ME.** COVID-19 vaccine design: the Janus face of immune enhancement. *Nature Reviews: Immunology* (2020) **20** 347–8
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41577-020-0323-4.pdf>
- [12] **Lee WS, Wheatley AK, Kent SJ, DeKosky BJ.** Antibody-dependent enhancement and SARS-CoV-2 vaccines and therapies. *Nature Microbiology* (2020) **5** 1185–91
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41564-020-00789-5.pdf>
- [13] **Emani VR, Pallipuram VK, Goswami KK, Maddula KR, Reddy R, Nakka AS, Panga S, Reddy NK, Reddy NK, Nandanoor D, Goswami S.** Increasing SARS-CoV2 cases, hospitalizations and deaths among the vaccinated elderly populations during the Omicron (B.1.1.529) variant surge in UK. *medRxiv* (2022)
<https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.06.28.22276926v2>

Appendix

Figure 10: *Residuals of cumulative “18-29” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 11: *Residuals of cumulative “30-39” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 12: *Residuals of cumulative “40-49” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 13: *Residuals of cumulative “50-59” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 14: *Residuals of cumulative “60-69” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 15: *Residuals of cumulative “70-79” dose-1 uptake.*

Figure 16: *Residuals of cumulative “80+” dose-1 uptake.*

